

Spanning Trails Joining Two Given Edges

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Abstract

A trail in G whose first edge is e_1 and whose last edge is e_2 is called an (e_1, e_2) -trail for $e_1, e_2 \in E(G)$. An (e_1, e_2) -trail T is called a spanning (e_1, e_2) -trail if $V(T) = V(G)$ and if every edge of G is incident with an internal vertex of T . An edge-cut X of a connected graph G is called essential if at least two components of $G - X$ contain at least one edge. In this paper, we prove that if a graph G has two edge-disjoint spanning trees, then either G has a spanning (e_1, e_2) -trail or $\{e_1, e_2\}$ is an essential edge-cut of a graph G .

Key words: graph, incident, trail, tree, spanning tree, essential edge-cut.

1. Basic Definitions and Notations on Graphs

A **graph** $G = (V, E)$ consists of two sets: a finite set V of elements called **vertices** and a finite set E of elements called **edges**. A graph $H = (V(H), E(H))$ is a **subgraph** of $G = (V(G), E(G))$ if $V(H) \subseteq V(G)$ and $E(H) \subseteq E(G)$. Let u and v be vertices of a graph G .

A (u, v) -**walk** W of G is a finite, alternating sequence

$$W: u = u_0 e_1 u_1 e_2 \dots u_{k-1} e_k u_k = v$$

of vertices and edges, beginning with vertex u and ending with vertex v , such that $e_i = u_{i-1} u_i$ for $i = 1, 2, \dots, k$. The number k (the number of occurrences of edges) is called the **length** of W . A (u, v) -walk is closed or open depending on whether $u = v$ or $u \neq v$. A (u, v) -**trail** is a (u, v) -walk in which no edge is repeated, while a (u, v) -**path** is a (u, v) -walk in which no vertex is repeated. A nontrivial closed trail of a graph G is referred to as a **circuit** of G , and a circuit $v_1 v_2 \dots v_n v_1$ ($n \geq 3$) whose n vertices v_i are distinct is called a **cycle**. An **acyclic** graph has no cycles. A graph G is **connected** if there exists a path between every pair of vertices in G . A graph that is not connected is **disconnected**. The **component** of a graph G is a maximal connected subgraph of G . We denote the number of components of G by $\omega(G)$.

A **tree** is a connected acyclic graph. An acyclic graph is also called a **forest**. A **spanning tree** of a graph G is a spanning subgraph of G that is a tree. Every connected graph G contains a spanning tree. Figure 1 depicts a connected graph G and its spanning tree.

Figure 1 A graph G and its spanning tree

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The spanning trees of a graph are said to be **edge-disjoint** if they have no common edges. A graph G and its two edge-disjoint spanning trees are shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2 A graph G and its two edge-disjoint spanning trees

An **edge-cut** of a graph G is a subset X of edges of G such that $G - X$ is disconnected. A **cut-edge** is an edge-cut consisting of a single edge. A k edge-cut is an edge-cut of k elements. The **edge connectivity** $\kappa'(G)$ of a graph G is the minimum cardinality of an edge-cut of G if G is nontrivial. A graph G is **k -edge-connected**, $k \geq 1$, if $\kappa'(G) \geq k$.

A **vertex-cut** of a graph G is a subset V' of vertices of G such that $G - V'$ is disconnected. A **cut-vertex** is a vertex-cut consisting of a single vertex. A k vertex-cut is a vertex-cut of k elements. The **connectivity** $\kappa(G)$ of a graph G is the minimum cardinality of a vertex-cut of G if G is nontrivial. A graph G is **k -connected**, $k \geq 1$, if $\kappa(G) \geq k$. Thus $\kappa(G) = 0$ if G is either trivial or disconnected.

An edge-cut X of a connected graph G is called **essential** if at least two components of $G - X$ contain at least one edge. A graph G with an essential edge-cut $X = \{e_1, e_2\}$ is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3 An essential edge-cut $\{e_1, e_2\}$ of a graph G

An **Eulerian trail** is a trail in a graph which visits every edge exactly once. An **Eulerian circuit** is an Eulerian trail which starts and ends on the same vertex. An **Eulerian graph** is a graph with an Eulerian circuit. A graph that has an Eulerian trail but not an Eulerian circuit is called **semi-Eulerian**. Figure 4 shows an Eulerian graph G with an Eulerian circuit $v_1 v_2 v_3 v_4 v_5 v_3 v_6 v_1$ and a semi-Eulerian graph G' with an Eulerian trail $v_1 v_2 v_3 v_1 v_4 v_3$.

Figure 4 An Eulerian graph G and a semi-Eulerian graph G'

1.1 Theorem

A connected graph G is Eulerian if and only if all vertices of G are of even degree.

Proof.

See [Catlin, P. A.].

1.2 Theorem

A connected graph G is semi-Eulerian if and only if it has exactly two vertices of odd degree.

Proof.

If G is semi-Eulerian then there is an Eulerian trail, P , in G . Suppose the trail begins at u_1 and ends at u_n . Except for the first listing of u_1 and the last listing of u_n , every time a vertex is listed, that accounts for two edges adjacent to that vertex, the one before it in the list and the one after it in the list. This trail uses every edge exactly once. So, every edge is accounted for and there are no repeats. Thus every degree must be even except for u_1 and u_n which must be odd.

Suppose u and v are the vertices of odd degree. Consider $G + uv$. This graph has all even degrees. By Theorem 1.1, $G + uv$ has an Eulerian circuit. This circuit uses the edge uv . Thus we have an Eulerian trail in G when we omit the edge uv .

2. Collapsible Graphs

2.1 Definition

For any graph H , define

$$O(H) = \{\text{odd-degree vertices of } H\}.$$

Let G be a graph, and let R be an even subset of $V(G)$.

An **R-subgraph** Γ of G is a subgraph $\Gamma \subseteq G$ such that both

$O(\Gamma) = R$ and $G - E(\Gamma)$ is connected.

2.2 Example

Figure 5 shows a graph G , its R -subgraph Γ and $G - E(\Gamma)$.

Figure 5 A graph G , its R -subgraph Γ and $G - E(\Gamma)$

2.3 Definition

A graph G is **collapsible** if G has an R -subgraph for every even set $R \subseteq V(G)$. The family of collapsible graphs is denoted CL .

2.4 Example

The graphs K_1 , K_3 and $K_{3,3} - e$ are all collapsible.

Figure 6 Collapsible graphs K_1 , K_3 and $K_{3,3} - e$

2.5 Definitions

An edge e of G is said to be **contracted** if it is deleted and its ends are identified. For a graph G with a subgraph H , the **contraction** G/H is the graph obtained from G by contracting all edges of H and deleting any resulting loops.

Figure 7 shows a graph G and contraction G/H .

Figure 7 A graph G and contraction G/H

2.6 Definitions

Every graph G has a unique collection of pairwise vertex-disjoint maximal collapsible subgraphs H_1, H_2, \dots, H_c such that $\bigcup_{i=1}^c V(H_i) = V(G)$. The **reduction** of G , denoted by G' , is the graph obtained from G by contracting each maximal collapsible subgraph H_i ($1 \leq i \leq c$), into a single vertex v_i . A graph G is **reduced** if $G=G'$. Figure 8 shows a graph G and the reduction G' of G by contracting the subgraphs H_1, H_2, H_3 and H_4 .

Figure 8 A graph G and the reduction G' of G

2.7 Theorem

For any graph G , define

$$F(G) = \max_{E \subseteq E(G)} (2[\omega(G - E) - 1] - |E|).$$

$F(G)$ is the minimum number of edges that must be added to G so that the resulting graph has two edge-disjoint spanning trees. If $F(G) \leq 1$, then exactly one of the following holds:

- (a) $G \in CL$;
- (b) G has a cut-edge.

Proof.

See [Catlin, P. A.].

2.8 Corollary

If $F(G) = 0$ then G has a spanning closed trail.

Proof.

See [Lai, H. J., Li, X., Poon, H. and Ou, Y.].

3. Associated Results on Two Edge-Disjoint Spanning Trees

3.1 Definitions

Let $e_1, e_2 \in E(G)$. A trail in G whose first edge is e_1 and whose last edge is e_2 is called an (e_1, e_2) -**trail**. An (e_1, e_2) -trail T is called a **spanning** (e_1, e_2) -**trail** if $V(T) = V(G)$ and if every edge of G is incident with an internal vertex of T . Figure 9 shows a graph G with a spanning (e_1, e_2) -trail.

Figure 9 Spanning (e_1, e_2) -trail of graph G

3.2 Lemma

Let H be a graph and let $R \subseteq V(H)$ have evenly many vertices in each component of H . Then there is a subgraph $\Gamma \subseteq H$ such that $O(\Gamma) = R$.

Proof.

See [Lai, H. J., Li, X., Poon, H. and Ou, Y.].

3.3 Definitions

Let e be an edge in G . Edge e is **subdivided** when it is replaced by a path of length 2 whose internal vertex, denoted by $v(e)$, has degree 2 in the resulting graph. The process of taking an edge e and replacing it by that path of length 2 is called **subdividing** e .

For a graph G and edges $e_1, e_2 \in E(G)$, and let $G(e_1, e_2)$ denote the graph obtained from G by subdividing both e_1 and e_2 . Thus,

$$V(G(e_1, e_2)) - V(G) = \{v(e_1), v(e_2)\}.$$

Figure 10 shows a graph G , a graph $G(e_1, e_2)$ obtained from G by subdividing both e_1 and e_2 .

Figure 10 A graph G and a graph $G(e_1, e_2)$

3.4 Theorem

Let G be a graph and let $e_1, e_2 \in E(G)$. If G has edge-disjoint spanning trees Γ_1 and Γ_2 such that $e_1, e_2 \notin E(\Gamma_1)$, then G has a spanning (e_1, e_2) -trail.

Proof.

Suppose that G, e_1, e_2, Γ_1 and Γ_2 satisfy the hypothesis. Denote $H = G - E(\Gamma_1)$. Since $E(\Gamma_2) \subseteq E(H)$, H is connected, and so by Lemma 3.2, there is a subgraph Γ of $H(e_1, e_2)$ such that

$$O(\Gamma) = O(G) \cup \{v(e_1), v(e_2)\}.$$

It follows that

$$O(G(e_1, e_2) - E(\Gamma)) = \{v(e_1), v(e_2)\},$$

and hence $G(e_1, e_2) - E(\Gamma)$ has an eulerian trail joining $v(e_1)$ and $v(e_2)$. This eulerian trail induces a spanning (e_1, e_2) -trail in G .

3.5 Definition

Let G be a graph and let $e_1, e_2 \in E(G)$. An $\{e_1, e_2\}$ -forbidden subgraph G_0 is any subgraph G_0 of G such that

- (i) $\{e_1, e_2\}$ is an edge-cut of G_0 ; and
- (ii) $F(G_0) = 0$.

A graph G and $\{e_1, e_2\}$ -forbidden subgraph G_0 are shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11 A graph G and $\{e_1, e_2\}$ -forbidden subgraph G_0

3.6 Lemma

Let G be a graph and let H be a connected subgraph of G . If $F(H) = 0$ and $F(G/H) = 0$, then H has edge-disjoint spanning trees, say U_1 and U_2 , and G/H has edge-disjoint spanning trees, say T_1 and T_2 . The pair (Γ_1, Γ_2) with

$$\Gamma_i = G[E(U_i) \cup E(T_j)] \quad (i, j \in \{1, 2\})$$

is a pair of edge-disjoint spanning trees of G .

Proof.

See [Lai, H. J., Li, X., Poon, H. and Ou, Y.].

3.7 Lemma

Let G be a graph, and let $e_1, e_2 \in E(G)$. Suppose that $F(G) = 0$ and G has no $\{e_1, e_2\}$ -forbidden subgraph. If G has no edge-disjoint spanning trees Γ_1 and Γ_2 such that $e_1, e_2 \notin E(\Gamma_1)$ and G is a graph with

$$|V(G)| + |E(G)| \text{ minimized,} \tag{1}$$

then for any proper nontrivial subgraph H of G , $F(H) \geq 1$.

Proof.

See [Lai, H. J., Li, X., Poon, H. and Ou, Y.].

3.8 Theorem

Let G be a graph, and let $e_1, e_2 \in E(G)$. If $F(G) = 0$ and if G has no $\{e_1, e_2\}$ -forbidden subgraph then G has two edge-disjoint spanning trees Γ_1 and Γ_2 such that $e_1, e_2 \notin E(\Gamma_1)$.

Proof.

By way of contradiction, let G be a graph with $|V(G)| + |E(G)|$ minimized and G does not satisfy the conclusion of the theorem. By Lemma 3.7, if G'' is a proper nontrivial subgraph of G , then

$$F(G'') \geq 1. \tag{2}$$

Since G has no $\{e_1, e_2\}$ -forbidden subgraph, $G - \{e_1, e_2\}$ is connected.

Hence, G has a spanning tree T with

$$E(T) \subseteq E(G - \{e_1, e_2\}).$$

Let F_1, F_2, \dots, F_k be the $\omega(G - E(T)) = k$ components of $G - E(T)$.

If $G - E(T)$ is a forest, then G is exactly $k - 1$ edges short of having two edge-disjoint spanning trees, and so $0 = F(G) = k - 1$. Therefore, $k = 1$ and so $\Gamma_1 = T$ and $\Gamma_2 = F_1$ are spanning trees that satisfy the conclusion of the theorem.

Therefore, we suppose that $G - E(T)$ is not a forest, and hence that at least one component F_i has a cycle. If F_i has at least one cycle, then we call F_i a **cyclic component** ($1 \leq i \leq k$). Define

$$\sigma(T) = \min_{1 \leq i \leq k} \{ |E(F_i)| : F_i \text{ is a cyclic component of } G - E(T) \}.$$

Choose a spanning tree T of $G - \{e_1, e_2\}$ so that

$$\omega(G - E(T)) \text{ is minimized} \tag{3}$$

and, subject to (3), so that

$$\sigma(T) \text{ is minimized.} \quad (4)$$

Let H be a cyclic component of $G - E(T)$ with

$$|E(H)| = \sigma(T).$$

Let T_1, T_2, \dots, T_m denote the components of $T[V(H)]$, and denote

$$V_i = V(T_i) \quad (1 \leq i \leq m).$$

Set $H^* = G[V(H)]$. Since H is a cyclic component, $|E(H)| \geq |V(H)|$, and so

$$\begin{aligned} |E(H^*)| &= |E(H)| + \sum_{i=1}^m |E(T_i)| \\ &\geq |V(H)| + (|V(H)| - m) \\ &= 2|V(H)| - m. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Let E be a subset of $E(H^*)$ such that

$F(H^*) = 2[\omega(H^* - E) - 1] - |E|$. If H' is any component of $H^* - E$, and E' a subset of $E(H')$ such that

$$F(H') = 2[\omega(H' - E') - 1] - |E'|,$$

then

$$\begin{aligned} F(H^*) &\geq 2[\omega(H^*) - (E \cup E') - 1] - |E \cup E'| \\ &= 2[\omega(H^* - E) + \omega(H' - E') - 2] - |E| - |E'| \\ &= 2[\omega(H^* - E) - 1] - |E| + 2[\omega(H' - E') - 1] - |E'| \\ &= F(H^*) + F(H'), \end{aligned}$$

and hence $F(H') = 0$. Using (2), we conclude that every component of $H^* - E$ is trivial, implying that $E = E(H^*)$ and $F(H^*) = 2[|V(H^*)| - 1] - |E(H^*)|$.

Again by (2),

$$|E(H^*)| = 2|V(H^*)| - 2 - F(H^*) \leq 2|V(H^*)| - 3. \quad (6)$$

Combination of (2.7) and (2.8) gives

$$m \geq 3. \quad (7)$$

For $i, j \in \{1, 2, \dots, m\}$, denote

$$Y_{i,j} = \{uv \in E(H) : u \in V_i, v \in V_j\},$$

and denote

$$Y = \bigcup_{i \neq j} Y_{i,j}.$$

Since H is connected, $Y \neq \emptyset$.

Case 1

Suppose $Y - \{e_1, e_2\} \neq \emptyset$. Therefore, $Y - \{e_1, e_2\}$ has an edge $z_1 z_2$, say, and without loss of generality, suppose that $z_1 \in V_1$ and $z_2 \in V_2$. Let C be the unique cycle of $T + z_1 z_2$. There are edges $u_1 v_1, u_2 v_2 \in E(T)$ with $u_i \notin V(H)$ and $v_i \in V_i$ ($1 \leq i \leq 2$).

Subcase 1 : Suppose that $z_1 z_2$ is a cut-edge of H .

Since H is cyclic, one of the components of $H - z_1 z_2$ has a cycle. Without loss of generality, we assume that the component of $H - z_1 z_2$ containing z_1 has a cycle. Then

$$T' = T + z_1 z_2 - u_2 v_2$$

is a spanning tree of $G - \{e_1, e_2\}$ such that

$$\sigma(T') \leq \sigma(T) - 1 \quad \text{and} \quad \omega(G - E(T)) = \omega(G - E(T')),$$

contrary to (3) and (4).

Subcase 2: Suppose that $z_1 z_2$ is not a cut-edge of H .

Hence, $H - z_1 z_2$ is connected. Define

$$T'' = T + z_1 z_2 - u_2 v_2$$

then

$$\omega(G - E(T'')) = \omega(G - E(T)) - 1,$$

contrary to (3).

Case 2

Suppose that $Y \subseteq \{e_1, e_2\}$. Since H is connected, (7) forces $Y = \{e_1, e_2\}$, $m = 3$, and $H[V_1]$, $H[V_2]$, and $H[V_3]$ must all be connected. Therefore, each $G[V_i]$ is an edge-disjoint union of the spanning connected graphs T_i and $H[V_i]$ ($1 \leq i \leq 3$), and hence $F(G[V_i]) = 0$. By (2) with $G'' = G[V_i]$, this forces $G[V_i] = K_1$ ($1 \leq i \leq 3$). Hence, H is acyclic, a contradiction. This completes Case 2 and the proof of the theorem.

3.9 Lemma

Let G be a graph, let H be a subgraph of G , let R be a subset of $V(G)$, and let S be an even subset of $V(H)$. If $H \in \text{CL}$, then G has a R -subgraph if and only if G has an $(R \Delta S)$ -subgraph.

Proof.

See [Lai, H. J., Li, X., Poon, H. and Ou, Y.].

3.10 Theorem

Let G be a graph and let $e_1, e_2 \in E(G)$. If G has two edge-disjoint spanning trees, then exactly one of the following holds:

- (i) G has a spanning (e_1, e_2) -trail;
- (ii) $\{e_1, e_2\}$ is an essential edge-cut of G .

Proof.

Suppose that G and $\{e_1, e_2\}$ satisfy the hypothesis of the theorem.

Thus, $F(G) = 0$.

Suppose that G has no $\{e_1, e_2\}$ -forbidden subgraph. By Theorem 3.8 and Theorem 3.4, G has a spanning (e_1, e_2) -trail, and (i) holds.

Next, suppose that G has an $\{e_1, e_2\}$ -forbidden subgraph, say G_0 . If $\{e_1, e_2\}$ is an edge-cut of G , then either (ii) holds or one component of $G - \{e_1, e_2\}$ is a single vertex. In the latter case, Corollary 2.8 implies (i). Suppose henceforth that $\{e_1, e_2\}$ is not an edge-cut of G .

Let G_1 and G_2 be the two components of $G_0 - \{e_1, e_2\}$. Since G_0 is a forbidden subgraph, $F(G_0) = 0$, and so G_0 has two edge-disjoint spanning trees. It follows that each component G_1 and G_2 of $G_0 - \{e_1, e_2\}$ has two edge-disjoint spanning trees, and so

$$F(G_1) = F(G_2) = 0. \quad (8)$$

By (8) and Theorem 2.7,

$$G_1, G_2 \in \text{CL}. \quad (9)$$

Since $\{e_1, e_2\}$ is not an edge-cut of G , it follows that $G - e_2$ is 2-edge-connected. Also, $F(G) = 0$ gives $F(G - e_2) \leq 1$, and so $G - e_2 \in \text{CL}$ by Theorem 2.7. By setting $S = O(G - e_2)$ in the definition of CL, we see that $G - e_2$ has a spanning eulerian subgraph H , say.

Define $e_1 = x_1x_2$ and $e_2 = y_1y_2$, where

$$x_1, y_1 \in V(G_1) \quad \text{and} \quad x_2, y_2 \in V(G_2).$$

Case 1 Suppose that $e_1 \in E(H)$.

Then $H - e_1$, has an eulerian (x_1, x_2) -trail that spans $G - \{e_1, e_2\}$.

Define

$$\Gamma = G - \{e_1, e_2\} - E(H).$$

and set $S = O(G - \{e_1, e_2\}) \Delta \{x_1, x_2\}$, i.e., $S = O(G - \{e_1, e_2\}) \Delta O(H - e_1)$. Then Γ is an S -subgraph of $G - \{e_1, e_2\}$, and Γ is the complement of $H - e_1$ in $G - \{e_1, e_2\}$. Set

$$R = \begin{cases} \{x_2, y_2\} & \text{if } x_2 \neq y_2 \\ \emptyset & \text{if } x_2 = y_2. \end{cases}$$

Then by Lemma 3.9, by (9), and since R is an even subset of $V(G_2)$, it follows that $G - \{e_1, e_2\}$ has an $(S \Delta R)$ -subgraph Γ' , say. Note that Γ' is the complement in $G - \{e_1, e_2\}$ of a spanning connected subgraph H' , say, where

$$O(H') = O(H - e_1) \Delta R = \{x_1, y_2\}.$$

By Theorem 1.2, H' contains an eulerian (x_1, y_2) -trail that spans $G - \{e_1, e_2\}$. By adding e_1 and e_2 to this trail, we extend it to a spanning (e_1, e_2) -trail of G .

Case 2 Suppose that $e_1 \notin E(H)$.

We imitate Case 1. Define

$$\Gamma = G - \{e_1, e_2\} - E(H),$$

and

$$S = O(G - \{e_1, e_2\}),$$

so that Γ is an S -subgraph of $G - \{e_1, e_2\}$ and Γ is the complement in $G - \{e_1, e_2\}$ of H .

Set

$$R = \begin{cases} \{x_2, y_2\} & \text{if } x_2 \neq y_2 \\ \emptyset & \text{if } x_2 = y_2. \end{cases}$$

By Lemma 3.9, by (9) and since $R = \{x_2, y_2\}$ is an even subset of $V(G_2)$ (set $R = \emptyset$ if $x_2 = y_2$), it follows that $G - \{e_1, e_2\}$ has an $(S \Delta R)$ -subgraph Γ' that is the complement in $G - \{e_1, e_2\}$ of a spanning (x_2, y_2) -trail. By adding e_1 at x_2 and e_2 at y_2 , we extend this trail to form a spanning (e_1, e_2) -trail in G . This completes the proof of the theorem.

4. Applications

Spanning trails in semi-Eulerian graphs are used rather extensively, as they're necessary to solve important problems in communication networks, parallel programming development and coding. Moreover, the corresponding theory underlies in many classic mathematical problems.

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